

From the four populations we studied, the predominant rice varieties cultivated nearby are most likely to have hybridized with the wild species (see table). In two populations we could not identify either the wild species or the probable cultivated varieties. The intermediate forms had characters from both wild and cultivated rice. Until flowering, the intermediate forms resembled the cultivated forms for most morphological characters (culm size, leaf blade length

and width, and tillering) and in gross morphology. After flowering, however, their panicle and grain characters made them easy to distinguish. The intermediate forms also produced panicles and grains that resembled the wild forms—slightly larger than the wild forms, but considerably smaller than the cultivated forms. We also observed some of the dominant characters of cultivated rice, such as leaf sheath pigmentation. All the wild forms had long green bristles

(absent in the cultivated forms), and the intermediate forms had red or purple bristles of intermediate length. We observed segregation for bristle length and color in the Samakhixai population, and for awn and grain characters in the Nongpin population.

The weedy forms are useful for identifying desirable segregates combining traits from the wild and cultivated forms. It may be worthwhile to screen the weedy forms for stress resistance traits. ■

Genetics

Genetics of anthocyanin pigmentation in rice

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We studied the inheritance of anthocyanin pigmentation of leaf sheaths in rice for eight crosses during the 1995 wet season at CRRI. Three deepwater varieties, Jalamagna, NDGR 410, and Kariawa (with purple pigmentation), and two tall indica varieties (TK deep-straw 34-774 and Khao Y Khao) were crossed during the 1993 wet season. Seeds of the parents, their F_1 s, and F_2 s were sown in small trays (50 × 40 cm). Twenty seedlings of each parent, 15 seedlings of each F_1 , and about 200-300 seedlings of each F_2 population were uprooted and washed 15 d after sowing. The frequency of plants with purple leaf sheaths was determined.

All F_1 seedlings of crosses between purple and green parents had purple pigmentation like that of the purple parent, indicating the trait's dominance (see table). F_2 populations of crosses between purple and green parents segregated into a 9 purple-7 green ratio, implying that two dominant complementary genes control purple pigmentation. F_1 and F_2 plants from two purple parents were all purple, and those from two green parents were all green.

Behavior of parents, F_1 , and F_2 with respect to purple pigmentation (15 d after seeding).

	Plants tested (no.)	Observed frequency		Expected ratio of purple to green	χ^2	P
		Purple (%)	Green (%)			
Parents						
Khao Y khao	20	0	20			
TK deep straw 34-774	20	0	20			
Jalamagna	20	20	0			
NDGR410	20	20	0			
Kariawa	20	20	0			
F_1						
Khao Y khao/Jalamagna	15	15	0			
Khao Y khao/NDGR 410	15	15	0			
Khao Y khao/Kariawa	15	15	0			
TK deep straw 34-774/Jalamagna	15	15	0			
TK deep straw 34-774/NDGR 410	15	15	0			
TK deep straw 34-774/Kariawa	15	15	0			
Jalamagna/NDGR 410	15	15	0			
Khao Y khao/TKdeep straw 34-774	15	0	15			
F_2						
Khao Y khao/Jalamagna	255	140	115	143.4:111.6 (9:7)	0.19	0.50-0.75
Khao Y khao/NDGR 410	276	158	118	155.3:120.8 (9:7)	0.11	0.50-0.75
Khao Y khao/Kariawa	266	151	115	149.6:116.4 (9:7)	0.03	0.75-0.90
TK deep straw 34-774/Jalamagna	226	120	106	127.1: 98.9 (9:7)	0.91	0.25-0.50
TK deep straw 34-774/NDGR 410	287	173	114	161.4:125.6 (9:7)	1.89	0.10-0.25
TK deep straw 34-774/Kariawa	328	201	127	184.5:143.5 (9:7)	3.37	0.05-0.10
Jalamagna/NDGR 410	305	305	0	-	-	-
Khao Y khao/TK deep straw 34-774	250	0	250	-	-	-

The data are consistent with the two dominant complementary genes for anthocyanin pigmentation of leaf sheath at the seedling stage. Purple pigmentation occurred when both genes were present; the absence of either or both resulted in green pigmentation like that in the green parents. ■

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